

Effect of Think-Pair Share Strategy on Students' Academic Achievement in Programming Concepts in Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of think-pair share strategy on students' academic achievement in programming concepts in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised 1,047 Senior Secondary School II (SS II) computer studies students from four co-educational secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The sample size of 248 SS II students was drawn using purposive random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was Programming Achievement Test (PAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability index of .82. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study showed that students who were taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy had improved academic achievement than their counterparts who were taught using lecture method. It was also found that male students had improved academic achievement than their female counterparts when exposed to think-pair share strategy. In line of the findings, the study recommended among others that Bayelsa State government should implement the think-pair-share strategy more widely in teaching programming concepts, and consider integrating it into other areas of the curriculum where applicable.

Keywords: Think-Pair Share Strategy, Lecture Method, Academic Achievement, Programming Concepts

Introduction

Computer programming is the set of instructions given to a computer, written in programming languages like Python, Java, or C++, that translates human language into machine-readable format (Sebesta, 2012; Zelle, 2016). Its long-term endeavor encompasses logical reasoning, problem-solving, and technical knowledge to realize the power of computer systems. This process is not easy and it needs sufficient knowledge in algorithms, data structures, and control which form the foundational concepts in programming.

Programming concepts are the foundational principles that guide the development and execution of software applications. Many algorithms provide step-by-step problem-solving instructions. Encapsulation, inheritance and polymorphism, three key concepts of object-oriented programming (OOP), increase code modularity and reusability (Stroustrup, 2013). Loops, along

with conditional statements—important control structures—allow developers to powerfully guide the flow of program execution (Sebesta, 2012). Programmers manage memory, an important programming aspect, by allocating and deallocating specific resources to optimize many application performances (Grune et al., 2012). Different approaches to solving problems are offered by programming models, such as functional, procedural, as well as declarative programming. Reliable and accurate software requires thorough debugging and testing throughout the software development lifecycle (Pressman, 2014).

A solid understanding of programming concepts is vital for creating efficient, reliable, and scalable software solutions. It provides a systematic approach to problem-solving through the application of algorithms, data structures, and control structures. This knowledge equips programmers with the ability to adapt to various programming languages and technologies, fostering versatility and innovation across diverse fields such as software development, artificial intelligence, and data science. Recognizing these immense benefits, computer studies have been incorporated into Nigeria's school curriculum at both the basic and senior secondary levels. Obadiaru (2020) noted that student performance in computer studies during the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) from 2014 to 2018 was consistently above average. However, despite the importance of programming knowledge and the positive trend in academic achievement, students' performance in external examinations like the SSCE conducted by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) has remained persistently low (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2021). This persistent underperformance raises concerns among Computer Science educators and researchers, as it indicates potential deficiencies in foundational knowledge crucial for the field. Several studies by Okechukwu and Ukeh (2022), Nwankwo and Ukeh (2023), Ukeh, et al. (2020) attributed students' underperformance in science related concepts to instructional approach. These teaching methods serve as tools or strategies that educators use to involve their students in meaningful activities, leading to the learning of ideas, values, and facts (Ukeh & Alibo, 2024).

The choice of instructional approach frequently emerges as a significant element influencing the academic success of computer studies students, primarily due to the prevalent use of teacher-centric methods by computer science educators. Moreover, numerous secondary schools in Nigeria face challenges related to inadequate facilities and infrastructure, which hinder effective teaching and learning, thereby, compromising the comprehensive grasp of programming concepts (Ukeh & Nwankwo, 2023). Additionally, even schools where these facilities are available record very low level of use (Obadiaru & Achuonye 2020). Also, studies have indicated that teachers in Nigerian secondary schools use lecture method in lesson delivery (Agwamba, 2014; Ogbu, 2018, Eke, 2021). As cited by Alibo and Tolowdun, (2024), the traditional method of teaching is still in use; as it offers the opportunity for teachers to pass across lots of information to the students and is useful for routine memorization. This lecture method is effective for delivering a large volume of information and is particularly suitable for managing large classes. However, despite its advantages, it does not foster students' creativity, critical thinking, inquiry, or scientific attitudes. Instead, it often promotes rote memorization, which can lead to rapid forgetting (Ogbu, 2018). To address these limitations, the lecture method, as a traditional instructional approach, can be enhanced by incorporating the think-pair-share strategy, which promotes active participation and collaborative learning among students.

The "Think-Pair-Share" strategy is a collaborative learning technique often used in classrooms to engage students in active learning and promote deeper understanding of the material. Think-Pair-Share (TPS) is a cooperative learning strategy that encourages students to work together to

solve problems or answer questions on an assigned topic (Andrew & Alexandria, 2015). Think-pair-share as the name goes involves the students in thinking about challenging academic tasks given by the teacher individually, pairing with other students to exchange ideas and sharing the idea with the larger class. Eke (2021), is of the view that think-pair-share also called multi-mode discussion is a learning technique that provides processing time and builds in wait-time which enhances the depth and breadth of thinking. The general idea of think pair share technique is having the students independently think or solve a problem quietly, then pair up and share their thoughts or solution with someone else. In the think-pair-share classroom, every student is an active learner. This strategy incorporates wait-time, verbal rehearsal, discussion, and cooperative learning. According to Usang and Okoli (2021), the implementation of the think-pair-share instructional strategy has been shown to positively correlate with increased academic achievement among students across various subjects.

Academic achievement refers to the measurable outcomes of learning and educational progress attained by students within an academic setting. These achievements can include various aspects such as grades, standardized test scores, completion of assignments, projects, presentations, research publications, awards, scholarships, and other recognitions related to academic pursuits. Studies by Azlina (2010), Eke (2021), and Egbai et al. (2022) revealed that students taught using Think-Pair-Share had a higher academic achievement gain score than those taught using lecture method. A study conducted by Usang and Okoli (2021), revealed that there was significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of the students taught using think-pair-share and those taught using conventional method in favour of think-pair share strategy. Although academic achievement is frequently viewed as a marker of individual success, studies consistently highlight subtle differences in educational outcomes between genders.

Gender encompasses the roles, behaviours, activities, and attributes that a society deems appropriate for men, women, and individuals with diverse identities. It also refers to the condition of being male or female, as described by Suzanne (2010). Educational practices and instructional strategies can either be gender-sensitive, promoting inclusivity, or exhibit gender biases that affect learning outcomes. Research findings have highlighted disparities in academic performance between genders, particularly in science-related courses. For instance, Egbai et al. (2022) found that male students outperformed their female counterparts when exposed to the think-pair-share strategy. Against this backdrop, the present study investigated the effect of the think-pair-share strategy on students' academic achievement in programming concepts in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching and learning programming concepts, a core topic in computer studies for senior secondary schools, can be challenging due to its abstract nature and the requirement for a deep understanding of underlying principles. The lecture method often falls short in fostering the active learning and critical thinking necessary to master these concepts. As a result, there is a pressing need to adopt alternative instructional strategies that encourage active engagement, collaborative learning, and a strong conceptual grasp among students. One such strategy is the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) approach, which promotes active participation, peer collaboration, and critical thinking through a structured process of individual reflection, small group discussion, and class-wide sharing. Although TPS has demonstrated effectiveness in various educational settings, its impact on improving students' academic performance in programming concepts remains an area that

requires further investigation. Therefore, the primary problem this study addressed was: What is the effect of Think-Pair-Share strategy on students' academic achievement in programming concepts in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of think-pair share strategy on students' academic achievement in programming concepts in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study investigated the:

1. effect of think-pair share strategy on computer studies students' academic achievement when taught programming concepts and those taught the same topic using lecture method;
2. influence of gender (male and female) on computer studies students' academic achievement when taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of computer studies students taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy.

H₀₃: There is no interaction effect of gender and method (think-pair share strategy) on students' academic achievement in programming concepts.

Research Method

Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. Nworgu (2015), described a quasi-experimental research design as one where it's not feasible to randomly allocate participants to both experimental and control groups. The population for the study comprised 1,047 Senior Secondary School II (SS II) computer studies students from four co-educational secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The sample size of 248 SS II students was drawn using purposive random sampling technique. It comprised 136 in the experimental group (75 male and 61 female students) and 112 in the control group. The instrument for data collection was Programming Achievement Test (PAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability index of .82.

Concurrently, conventional computer studies teachers were trained on implementing the think-pair-share strategy to teach students in the experimental group. A lesson plan centered around programming concepts was devised. This treatment lasted for four (4) weeks, and it also aligned with the standard school schedule. The timetable allocated one (1) double period (80 minutes) and one (1) single period (40 minutes) for computer studies every week. These periods were used to teach the students for four (4) weeks, where each topic lasted for one (1) week. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The choice for the use of ANCOVA is because intact classes were used and initial differences cannot be guaranteed. The null hypothesis was not rejected if probability value is less than or equal to the significant value of .05 ($P \leq 0.05$) and if otherwise ($P > .05$), it was rejected.

Results Presentation

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy and those taught using lecture method

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Experimental	136	32.09	4.60	34.56	5.20	2.47
Control	112	31.45	4.43	32.85	5.09	1.40
Mean Diff.						1.07

The table presents the mean achievement scores and standard deviations for students taught programming concepts using two different methods: think-pair share strategy and lecture method. The experimental group, taught with think-pair share, had a mean pre-test score of 32.09 and a mean post-test score of 34.56, with a mean gain of 2.47. The control group, taught with the lecture method, had a mean pre-test score of 31.45 and a mean post-test score of 32.85, with a mean gain of 1.40. The standard deviations for both groups on both tests are also provided. The findings of the study showed that students who were taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy had improved academic achievement than their counterparts who were taught using lecture method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught programming concepts using think-pair strategy

Gender	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Male	75	31.06	4.42	34.58	5.42	3.52
Female	61	30.44	4.11	33.44	4.67	3.00
Mean Diff.						.52

This table presents the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female computer studies students who learned programming concepts through the think-pair-share method. The data reveals that there were 75 male and 61 female students in the study. Before instruction, the average pre-test score for males was 31.06 with a standard deviation of 4.42, while females scored 30.44 with a standard deviation of 4.11. After the instruction, the mean post-test scores were 34.58 for males (standard deviation: 5.42) and 33.44 for females (standard deviation: 4.67). Finally, the table shows a mean difference of 0.52 in post-test scores between males and females, indicating a slight advantage for male students.

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of computer studies students taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of computer studies students taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy and those taught using lecture method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	43.80	2	21.90	3.44	.020	Rejected
Intercept	31.11	1	31.11	9.06	.000	
Pretest	44.06	1	44.06			
Group	53.67	1	53.67	4.56	.020	
Error	172.64	246	.940	8.54		
Total	345.28	248				
Corrected Total	371.45	247				

The analysis presented in Table 3 indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of computer studies students taught programming concepts using the Think-Pair-Share strategy compared to those taught via the lecture method. The F-value of 4.56 with a significance level of .020 suggests that the null hypothesis (Ho₁), which posits no significant

difference between the two teaching methods, is rejected. The corrected model's significance at .020 reinforces the effectiveness of the Think-Pair-Share strategy in enhancing student achievement in programming concepts. These results imply that instructional strategies significantly impact students' learning outcomes, with collaborative approaches yielding better performance than traditional lectures.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts with think-pair share strategy.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts using think-pair share strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	36.98	2	18.49	3.14	.00	Rejected
Intercept	11.01	1	11.01	3.09	.00	
Pretest	14.42	1	14.42			
Gender	13.36	1	13.36	6.51	.00	
Error	704.84	134	5.26	5.09	.01	
Total	780.61	136				
Corrected Total	791.56	133				

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) presented in Table 4 indicates that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female computer studies students taught programming concepts using the think-pair-share strategy, as evidenced by the F-value of 6.51 and a significance level (Sig.) of .00. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀₂), which posited no significant difference in achievement scores based on gender. Additionally, the corrected model shows a significant overall effect, with an F-value of 3.14 and a significance level of .00, further supporting the conclusion that gender influences achievement in this educational context. Therefore, it can be inferred that teaching strategies such as think-pair-share may yield different outcomes for male and female students in computer studies.

H₀₃: There is no interaction effect of gender and method (think-pair share strategy) on students' academic achievement in programming concepts.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the interaction effect of gender and method (think-pair share strategy) on computer studies students' achievement in programming concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	37.36	2	18.68	6.09	.00	
Intercept	20.49	1	20.49	4.54	.00	
Method*Gender	16.56	1	16.56	5.11	.01	Rejected
Error	910.89	246	3.81			
Total	985.30	248				
Corrected Total	991.45	247				

The Type III Sum of Squares for the interaction between method and gender is 16.56, with a corresponding F-value of 5.11 and a significance level of 0.01, indicating a statistically significant interaction effect. Since the null hypothesis (H_0) states that there is no interaction effect, the results lead to its rejection, suggesting that the combination of gender and teaching method significantly influences students' academic performance. Therefore, educators should consider these factors when implementing instructional strategies to enhance learning outcomes in programming concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The study's results indicated that students instructed in programming concepts through the think-pair-share strategy achieved better academic performance compared to those taught using traditional lectures. This finding aligns with the research of Usang and Okoli (2021), Eke (2021), and Egbai et al. (2022), who asserted that students utilizing the think-pair-share method demonstrated greater academic success than their lecture-taught peers. Furthermore, the results support Andrew and Alexandria's (2015) conclusion that implementing the think-pair-share approach significantly enhances students' academic performance. Additionally, Adekunle (2015) found that students taught via guided discovery and think-pair-share techniques had notably higher posttest mean scores than those instructed through conventional lecture methods. The study also revealed that male students exhibited superior academic achievement compared to female students when engaged with the think-pair-share strategy. This observation is consistent with the findings of Egbai et al. (2022), who noted that male students outperformed their female counterparts academically.

Conclusion

The study's findings indicate that the think-pair-share strategy significantly enhances students' academic achievement in programming concepts compared to traditional lecture methods. This interactive approach fosters collaboration and deeper understanding among peers, leading to improved learning outcomes. As teachers seek effective teaching methods, incorporating strategies like think-pair-share can be instrumental in engaging students and promoting better academic performance. These results highlight the importance of innovative teaching techniques in the evolving landscape of education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Bayelsa State government should implement the think-pair-share strategy more widely in teaching programming concepts, and consider integrating it into other areas of the curriculum where applicable.
2. The school administrators should emphasize collaborative learning environments where students of all genders can work together and learn from each other. Encourage group discussions, peer teaching, and collaborative projects that promote teamwork and mutual support.

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